

BLENDED LEARNING IMPLEMENTATION AND STUDENTS' SATISFACTION IN CABUYAO CITY PRIVATE SCHOOLS

Beverly A. Fadriquelan

School of Graduate Studies, Laguna College of Business and Arts, Calamba City, Laguna, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

The main focus of this study was to determine the current levels of blended learning implementation and students' satisfaction and to rule out the significant difference between the two variables and the significant relationship between the responses of the two groups of respondents in some of the private schools in Cabuyao City. The proposed action plan was to manage blended learning implementation and increase the satisfaction level of the students in private schools was the output of this study. This study utilized the quantitative descriptive correlational research design. Through stratified sampling technique, the respondents of the study were 48 teachers and 202 students from (three) 3 different private schools in Cabuyao City. Adopted questionnaires were used as survey instruments for the gathering of data. Using the four-point Likert Scale, the simple mean, t-test, and Pearson r, findings revealed that there was a significant difference between the assessment of teachers and students in blended learning implementation. There was a significant difference between the assessment of teachers and students in Social and Technical Design. There was no significant difference between the assessment of teachers and students in terms of Pedagogical Design. Blended learning implementation had significant relationship with students' satisfaction specifically in Interaction, Instruction, Instructor, Course Management, and Technology.

Keywords: *blended learning implementation, students' satisfaction, private schools*

INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic presented difficulties for several sectors, particularly in defending fundamental rights. Basic education was one of the sectors that severely impacted as schools and community learning centers are closed for the physical conduct of lessons as part of the steps to contain the COVID-19. (DO 012 s. 2020). The secretary of the Department of Education stated that the protection of the safety, health, and well-being of children, instructors, and staff, as well as the avoidance of the spread of COVID-19, was the first principle to adhered and devoted. At the same time, learning must continue.

Blended Learning has become the latest and utmost prevalent arrangement of education today. In the past decade, it has a main influence on postsecondary education and the changes is growing. In general, Blended Learning is a combination of online learning that takes place in the Internet and referred to as “e-learning” besides face-to-face classes referred towards as the “traditional learning”. (Stern, 2020).

The environment is shifting. This is not somewhat original but due to a great worldwide interconnectedness and a growing way of alteration it has hardly develop for humans to preserve their step thru the economical, social, and technological developments. The acronym VUCA World defines about significant aspects of developments and hence has gained fame these days. VUCA stands for Volatility, Uncertainty, Complexity and Ambiguity (Burgartz, 2016).

Similarly, online setup is never a new arrangement in education. It has origin in distance instruction and the beginning of digital tools that enable the effective and consistent transfer of discussions, virtual teaching space sessions, and other materials for instructions and assessments in the form of the Internet. In January 2020 the COVID-19 breached the Philippines. It brought a lot of changes in Philippine Educational System. Since its outbreak in late December 2019, COVID-19 has caused chaos across the world and line any critical sector, education has been hit hard. Schools, colleges, universities, and students have been severely affected. In the same way, Philippine educational system is striving to continue at this difficult time. With the help of the government, the Department of Education pursued the School Year 2020 – 2021. Despite of all the adversities along the way, the DepEd did not allow the education to stop. The Department of Education offers variety of modalities to fit in the available way of learning of the Filipino families. One of these modalities is the Blended Learning.

Moreover, blended learning has developed an essential factor of higher education, as is apparent by a stable appearance and growth of online program presents and online academic professional degree programs. In most area, students can take a lead in a wide range of online learning opportunities and choose any of the available plans. Though, taking from among the variety of choices for pursuing one’s theoretical goals through an online program can be a test. In the Philippines, specifically in public schools, blended learning was introduced due to the COVID-19. But today, it is endemic, the people are living with the COVID-19. Blended learning is not only for the COVID-19 today, but in any

circumstances that might be along the way. Before, when there is a typhoon in the Philippines, automatically the classes are cancelled. But today, the educational system has an option which is the blended learning. Through this, learning will not be compromised. (Tumenio, 2021).

In this difficult time, it is hard to achieve students' satisfaction. However, with all the hard work of all the people in the educational system, it is attainable. Engagement and contentment have a substantial and inversely associated relationship. Additionally, there was a marginally significant but positive association between engagement and satisfaction with their overall performances. Regardless of how they performed, students were usually happy with the learning design philosophy. However, students voiced concerns about a lack of tutor assistance and group-wide technical challenges.

Correspondingly, Blended Learning (BL) in the Philippines is not that easy. Unlike in other country, blended learning is existing during pre-pandemic. Other countries practiced blended learning in different schools set up. However, in the Philippines it is new to all the learners especially to those ordinary Filipino. Not everyone can afford hybrid learning since it has a lot of preparations. Aside from going to school to attend face to face classes, learners should have an internet connection and a good gadget that will go along with the discussion. Since we are part of third world country, it is not easy for ordinary parents to provide these necessities to their children.

This crisis in educational system has brought some unknown talents among the stakeholders at different levels. Specifically, a strong and open communication that was built between external and internal stakeholders in school. In this situation, leaders can showcase their capabilities in management that is essential to the institution. That is why, this study conducted to determine the implementation of the Blended Learning in private schools and the level of satisfaction of students. With this, leaders will find it simple to deal with any scenario that may arise in the future and to offer support in order to ensure that education will be successful if it does.

Research Questions

This study aimed to assess the implementation of Blended Learning in Cabuyao City Private Schools and its relation to the students' level of satisfaction.

Specifically, the study sought answers to the following:

1. What is the implementation level of Blended Learning in Cabuyao City private schools as assessed by teachers and students in terms of:
 - 1.1 Pedagogical Design,
 - 1.2 Social Design, and
 - 1.3 Technical Design?
2. Is there a significant difference between the assessment of teachers and students in Blended Learning Implementation in Cabuyao City Private Schools?
3. What is the satisfaction level of students in Cabuyao City Private Schools as assessed by teachers and students in terms of:

- 3.1 Interaction,
 - 3.2 Instruction,
 - 3.3 Instructor,
 - 3.4 Course Management, and
 - 3.5 Technology?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the assessed level of blended learning implementation and students' satisfaction in Cabuyao City Private Schools?
 5. Based on the findings of the study, what action plan may be proposed?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study utilized the Descriptive Correlational research design. Descriptive studies are used when small thing is known about a certain phenomenon. This design seeks to observe, describe, and document several sides of an occurrence. This also searches for cause and effect that is related to the occurrences. Descriptive design define what actually happens and regulate the frequency with what it occurs and classifies the evidence. Correlational designs intricate the systematic investigation of the nature of connections or relations between and among the independent and dependent variables. This design used to examine if changes in one or more variable are related to other variable. This is also known as co-variance. Correlations analyze direction, degree, magnitude, and strength of the relationships.

Hence, this design is suited to this study since it sought to determine the relationship between the assessed level of blended learning implementation and students' satisfaction in Cabuyao City Private Schools.

Research Locale

This study was conducted in selected private schools in the Division of Cabuyao City. The researcher has chosen to conduct this study among this schools since she has been in the private school teaching for 3 years and familiar with the nature of the policies and guidelines implemented in the private schools.

City Schools Division of Cabuyao has been noted for having many private schools who have been permitted to operate and others have obtained their recognition. Given these realities, the researcher found it easy to determine the private schools be involved in the study, however, the schools have given the opportunities to accept or decline the request of the researcher concerning the conduct of this study. For some schools that the request was declined, the researcher was still able to conduct the study with the other schools who have expressed their willingness to be part of this study.

Population and Sampling

This study utilized the Stratified Sampling Technique which is a sampling method that involves a partition of population into smaller sub-groups known as strata. A stratified random selection divides the population into smaller subgroups called strata. The strata were constructed based on members' common features of traits such as wealth or educational level in stratified random sampling, or stratification. The entire population was divided into homogeneous groups called strata in samples are chosen from each stratum.

Respondents of the Study

This study involved the three (3) private schools in Cabuyao City that are implementing the Blended Learning Modality. The table shows how the respondents were distributed.

Table A

Distribution of Respondents of the Study

Private Schools	Population	Sample Size (Teachers)	Sample Size (Students)	Total Sample Size	Percentage
A	680	22	120	142	56.8 %
B	245	11	22	33	13.20 %
C	388	15	60	75	30 %
Total	1313	48	202	250	100%

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher personally appeared and hand-in the letter of request to the administrative office of three selected private schools in Cabuyao City requesting the permission to conduct the study on their respective schools. Upon the approval to conduct the study, the researcher utilized the google forms to distribute the instrument to the respondents and avoid physical contact with the respondents in accordance with the minimum health protocols due to the COVID-19 Pandemic.

Instrument

The prime instruments that was utilized in this study are the adopted but modified survey questionnaires. To measure the level of blended learning implementation to both teachers and students, the modified version of test questionnaire used.

This assessment used questions that are based on the implementation of blended learning today. It castoff a 4-point Likert Scale with the options: Fully Implemented,

Implemented, Partially Implemented, and Not Implemented. The questionnaire was divided into three categories to assess different indicators of blended learning implementation: (a) Pedagogical Design, 7 questions; (b) Social Design, 7 questions; and (c) Technical Design, 6 questions.

To measure the students' satisfaction for blended learning implementation, an adopted research questionnaire was used. This modified assessment used questions that are based on the students' satisfaction. It also used a 4-point Likert Scale with the options: Very Satisfied, Satisfied, Dissatisfied, and Very Dissatisfied. The questionnaire was divided into five categories to assess different indicators of students' satisfaction: (a) Interaction, 9 questions; (b) Instruction, 12 questions; (c) Instructor, 5 questions; (d) Course Management, 3 questions; and (e) Technology, 6 questions.

The research instrument was adopted from the study of Ahmed ANKIT, PhD, Mirna Nachouki, PhD, and Mahmoud Abou Jaaj, PhD (2012) to measure the satisfaction level of blended learning. The research instrument undergone a pilot testing in one of the private schools in Cabuyao City with 20 respondents. The questionnaire regarding the level of implementation of blended learning in Cabuyao City Private Schools had a Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient of .964 while the part intended to measure students' satisfaction had a Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient of .963 which were both considered as highly reliable.

Ethical Considerations

The consideration of these issues were necessary to ensure privacy and security of participants. Among the significant ethical issues considered in the research process include consent and confidentiality. The researchers relayed all the important details and the aim of the study to secure consent from the respondents. By explaining these vital details, respondents were to understand their role in the completion of the study. The confidentiality of the respondents was ensured by not disclosing their names where they are currently affiliated. Only relevant information needed to answer the specific research questions will be included. The data pooled in this study were kept confidential and were solely used for the purpose of this study.

Treatment of Quantitative Data

The following statistical tools were utilized in this study.

1. Mean and Likert Scale were utilized in identifying the level of implementation of the Blended learning and the students' Satisfaction.
2. T-test was used to determine the significant difference between the assessments of the two groups of respondents on the level of implementation of the Blended Learning and students' satisfaction.
3. The Pearson Product Correlation Coefficient was applied in determining the significant relationship between the assessed level of blended learning and students' satisfaction.

RESULTS

Research Question 1. What is the implementation level of Blended Learning in Cabuyao City Private Schools as assessed by teachers and students in terms of Pedagogical Design, Social Design, and Technical Design?

1.1 Blended Learning in terms of Pedagogical Design

The Implementation Level of Blended Learning in Cabuyao City Private Schools as assessed by Teachers and Students in terms of Pedagogical Design had a general assessment of 3.45 which was verbally interpreted as Strongly Agree or Fully Implemented.

All indicators were verbally interpreted as Fully Implemented. Furthermore, the indicator *“The learning objectives are clearly stated in each lesson”* had the highest computed mean of 3.61 meanwhile, the indicator *“The structure of the environment helps me focus on learning”* had the lowest computed mean of 3.37.

Table 1.1

Implementation Level of Blended Learning in Cabuyao City Private Schools as assessed by Teachers and Students in terms of Pedagogical Design

Indicators in terms of Pedagogical Design	Teacher s		Students		Composi te		Ran k
	$\bar{X}$	VI	$\bar{X}$	VI	$\bar{X}$	VI	
1. The learning objectives are clearly stated in each lesson.	3.82	SA	3.40	SA	3.61	SA	1
2. The organization of each lesson is easy to follow.	3.59	SA	3.28	SA	3.43	SA	4
3. The structure of the environment helps me focus on learning.	3.47	SA	3.28	SA	3.37	SA	7
4. Expectations of assignments are clearly stated.	3.41	SA	3.36	SA	3.39	SA	5.5
5. Activities are planned carefully.	3.65	SA	3.42	SA	3.53	SA	2
6. The content of the course worked well in a blended learning environment.	3.47	SA	3.31	SA	3.39	SA	5.5
7. The presentation of the course content was clear.	3.53	SA	3.35	SA	3.44	SA	3
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.56	SA	3.34	SA	3.45	S A/ FI	

Legend:

- 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/ Fully Implemented
- 2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A)/ Implemented
- 1.75 – 2.49 Disagree (D)/ Partially Implemented
- 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/ Not Implemented

It can be concluded that blended learning in Cabuyao City Private Schools utilized the Pedagogical Design effectively. It is also evident that in each lesson the learning objectives are clearly stated and understood by teachers and students. This further means that the teachers were able to craft and state the objectives clearly and can be attained at the end of the lesson. However, it can also be gleaned in the results that as assessed by both groups of respondents there is still a need to re-structure or improve the structure of learning environment which might help the learners attain better focus on their studies. There are a lot of distractions that might come along the way, so, a place that will help the learners focus on the learning is a big help for them to attain the learning objectives.

In the study conducted by Montemayor (2022), she had explicated that in spite of the hurdles posed by the epidemic, the Department of Education, along with other governmental organizations and partners, made progress in reinstating face-to-face classes this school year. She further explained that implementing in-person education in the midst of the COVID-19 outbreak was risky and fraught with difficulty. However, the information available indicates that beginning in-person lessons as soon as feasible delivers more benefits than hazards when it comes to learning to live with endemic COVID-19.

1.2 Blended Learning in terms of Social Design

The Implementation Level of Blended Learning in Cabuyao City Private Schools as assessed by Teachers and Students in terms of **Social Design** had a general assessment of **3.44** which was verbally interpreted as **Strongly Agree or Fully Implemented**.

Table 1.2

Implementation Level of Blended Learning in Cabuyao City Private Schools as assessed by Teachers and Students in terms of Social Design

Indicators in terms of Social Design	Teachers		Students		Composite		Rank
	$\bar{X}$	VI	$\bar{X}$	VI	$\bar{X}$	VI	
1. I communicate with other students in this subject electronically.	3.82	SA	3.22	A	3.52	SA	3
2. I can ask my teacher what I do not understand.	3.71	SA	3.42	SA	3.56	SA	1.5

3. I can ask other students what I do not understand.	3.47	SA	3.28	SA	3.38	SA	5
4. Other students respond promptly to my requests for help.	3.53	SA	3.24	A	3.39	SA	4
5. The teachers give me quick comments on my work.	3.53	SA	3.21	A	3.37	SA	6
6. My classmates and I regularly evaluate each other's work.	3.47	SA	3.13	A	3.30	SA	7
7. I was supported by a positive attitude from my teacher and my classmates.	3.71	SA	3.41	SA	3.56	SA	1.5
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.61	SA	3.27	SA	3.44	SA/FI	

Legend:

3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/ Fully Implemented

2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A)/ Implemented

1.75 – 2.49 Disagree (D)/ Partially Implemented

1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/ Not Implemented

All indicators were verbally interpreted as Fully Implemented. Furthermore, the indicators *“I can ask my teacher what I do not understand”* and *“I was supported by a positive attitude from my teacher and my classmates”* both had the highest computed mean of 3.56 meanwhile, the indicator *“My classmates and I regularly evaluate each other's work”* had the lowest computed mean of 3.30.

This means that blended learning in Cabuyao City Private Schools practice the Social Design successfully. It is also apparent that the social relationship between teachers and students during blended learning is transparent and constructive. The results further implies that the learners might have better condition and interest for learning if they have harmonious social relationship with usual people they are dealing with such as the teachers and their classmates. On the other hand, it turned out that learners have given less agreement on evaluating the works of their classmates. This might be due to the fact that their teachers conduct less activities that would enable the learner to check the work of their classmates. In some points it might affect the self-confidence and esteem of learners where they may feel embarrassed mostly, when they got low scores or worst, failing grades.

In the study conducted by McGreen (2020), there are learners who do not want to be judged by others. Even if it is part of their learning tasks, there are learners who found it hard to accept their low scores which manifest their performance. There are learners who might considered it as humiliating on their parts, teachers shall be sensitive about this issue. Teachers should approach the learners in a most sensitive way to avoid

misunderstanding that might lead to the learners to stop going to school or to stop being comfortable in socializing with their peers.

1.3 Blended Learning in terms of Technical Design

Table 1.3

Implementation Level of Blended Learning in Cabuyao City Private Schools as assessed by Teachers and Students in terms of Technical Design

Indicators in terms of Technical Design	Teachers		Students		Composite		Rank
	$\bar{X}$	VI	$\bar{X}$	VI	$\bar{X}$	VI	
1. I can access the learning activities at times convenient to me	3.88	SA	3.29	SA	3.59	SA	1
2. The online material is available at locations suitable for me	3.47	SA	3.23	A	3.35	SA	4
3. I am allowed to work at my own speed to achieve my learning objectives	3.53	SA	3.23	A	3.38	SA	3
4. I decided how much I want to learn in a given period	3.47	SA	3.09	A	3.28	SA	5
5. I decide when I want to learn	3.65	SA	2.83	A	3.24	A	6
6. Using blended learning allowed me to explore the interest of my own	3.65	SA	3.30	A	3.47	SA	2
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.61	SA	3.16	A	3.39	SA/VI	

Legend:

3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/ Fully Implemented

2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A)/ Implemented

1.75 – 2.49 Disagree (D)/ Partially Implemented

1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/ Not Implemented

The implementation level of blended learning in Cabuyao City Private Schools as assessed by teachers and students in terms of **Technical Design** had a general assessment of **3.39** which was verbally interpreted as **Strongly Agree or Fully Implemented**.

Most indicators were verbally interpreted as Fully Implemented. Furthermore, the indicator *“I can access the learning activities at times convenient to me”* had the highest computed mean of 3.59 meanwhile, the indicator *“I decide when I want to learn”* had the lowest computed mean of 3.24.

This means that blended learning in Cabuyao City Private Schools promotes the Technical Design efficiently. It is also apparent that through blended learning, students can study in their most convenient time. With the combination of face to face classes and online classes, students has the additional time to study even after the school hours since they are in their comfort place and time – their home. This further shows that it is one of the major features of the blended learning which provides time for the learners to accomplish the tasks on their convenient time, when they are in the mood, when they are at the height of their interests to do their learning tasks.

The main objective of cognitive flexibility was to help improve the capacity of the learner to understand different scenarios that rely on learning from multiple philosophical viewpoints in diverse and ill-structured domains, which reflect several real-life situations. The theory was an adjunct to constructivist techniques and strongly relates to the significance of knowledge building. It does, however, had an objectivist foundation. This offers a variety of instruction design heuristics that resist over-simplifying Instruction by providing real-world examples, providing numerous interconnected representations of information to increase transmission, and requiring construction of information by learners. (James, 2018).

Research Question 2. What is the Students’ satisfaction level in Cabuyao City Private Schools in terms of Interaction, Instruction, Instructor, Course Management, and Technology?

2.1 Students’ Satisfaction in terms of Interaction

Table 2.1

Students’ Satisfaction Level in Cabuyao City Private Schools in terms of Interaction

Indicators in terms of Interaction	$\bar{X}$	VI	Rank
1. A blended learning session keeps me always alert and focused.	3.13	A	6
2. Interaction is adequately maintained with the lecturer when he/she is on the other side of the blended learning classroom.	3.25	SA	5
3. Having students from the opposite gender on the other side of the blended learning classroom listening to what I say might restrict my participation.	2.80	A	9

4. A blended learning course makes it more important for students to visit the lecturer during office-hours.	3.08	A	7
5. I cannot interrupt the lecturer to ask a question when he/she is on the other side of the blended learning classroom.	2.92	A	8
6. I am satisfied with the quality of interaction between all involved parties.	3.32	SA	3
7. I am satisfied with the process of collaboration activities during the course.	3.35	SA	2
8. I am satisfied with the way I interact with other students.	3.40	SA	1
9. I am satisfied with my participation in the class.	3.28	SA	4
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.17	A/S	

Legend:

3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/ Very Satisfied

2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A)/ Satisfied

1.75 – 2.49 Disagree (D)/ Dissatisfied

1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/ Very Dissatisfied

The students' satisfaction level in Cabuyao City Private Schools in terms of **Interaction** had a general assessment of **3.17** which was verbally interpreted as **Agree or Satisfied**.

Most of the indicators were verbally interpreted as Very Satisfied. Furthermore, the indicator *"I am satisfied with the way I interact with other students"* had the highest computed mean of 3.40 meanwhile, the indicator *"Having students from the opposite gender on the other side of the blended learning classroom listening to what I say might restrict my participation"* had the lowest computed mean of 2.80.

The result simple denote that students' satisfaction in Cabuyao City Private Schools in terms of interaction is satisfying. With the combination of face to face classes and online classes the students still able to interact with their peers and their teachers even on the other side of the virtual classroom. The result also indicate that the learners love to see and deal with their teachers and classmates physically. They loved to interact with them, share their thoughts and feelings. On the other hand, the learners still have an issue towards the opposite gender, they feel being restricted. This shows that the learners still have to understand the GAD or gender and equality in learning. Also, it manifests the needs for the teachers in interfere and explains to the class the importance of respecting one another despite of their sex and background.

As per the results of the study conducted by Bernardo (2021) about the knowledge Gender and Equality. Learners shall be given the chance to understand the roles of GAD on their studies. They shall also been given the chance to understand their rights and the law related to GAD.

Further, according to Batang (2021) Good behavior is the poster child of effective classroom management and can be achieved by clearly communicating your behavioral expectations to students. The implementation of a classroom behavior policy will allow you to outline the types of behavior you expect to see demonstrated by students in your class. Communicating your class' behavior policy at the beginning of the term will set the tone for the rest of the year.

2.2 Students' Satisfaction in terms of Instruction

The students' satisfaction level in Cabuyao City Private Schools in terms of **Instruction** had a general assessment of **3.21** which was verbally interpreted as **Agree or Satisfied**.

Most of the indicators were verbally interpreted as Satisfied. Furthermore, the indicators *"I am satisfied with the level of effort this course required"*, *"I am satisfied with how I am able to apply what I have learned in this course"*, and *"I enjoy working on assignments by myself"* had the highest computed mean of 3.36 meanwhile, the indicator *"Compared to face-to-face course settings, I am more satisfied with this learning experience"* had the lowest computed mean of 2.90.

Table 2.2

Students' Satisfaction Level in Cabuyao City Private Schools in terms of Instruction

Indicators in terms of Instruction	$\bar{X}$	VI	Rank
1. The use of blended learning technology in this course encourages me to learn independently.	3.34	SA	4
2. My understanding is improved compared to similar courses I studied before.	3.27	SA	5
3. My performance in exams is improved compared to similar courses I studied before.	3.22	A	8.5
4. I am satisfied with the level of effort this course required.	3.36	SA	2
5. I am satisfied with my performance in this course.	3.23	A	6.5
6. I believe I will be satisfied with my final grade in the course.	3.23	A	6.5
7. I am satisfied with how I am able to apply what I have learned in this course.	3.36	SA	2
8. If I had known this was going to be a blended learning class, I would have taken it right away.	3.04	A	40
9. I am willing to take another course using the blended learning delivery mode.	2.96	A	11
10. I am satisfied enough with this course to recommend it to others.	3.22	A	8.5

11. Compared to face-to-face course settings, I am more satisfied with this learning experience.	2.90	A	12
12. I enjoy working on assignments by myself.	3.36	SA	2
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.21	A/S	

Legend:

3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/ Very Satisfied

2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A)/ Satisfied

1.75 – 2.49 Disagree (D)/ Dissatisfied

1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/ Very Dissatisfied

Table 2.2 disclose that the learners have expressed that they were Very Satisfied when regards to the level of effort required by the course they are taking. Also, they were able to apply what they have learned. These are the very core of authentic learning, that the learners understand the course they are taking and how they apply it to their daily lives. After the two years restriction of physical classes, the learners were able to enjoy the blended learning wherein they were given the chance to fully understand what the course is all about and make them realize the worth of these course on their daily living. The learners have also expressed that they were highly satisfied in the blended learning and enjoyed working on their homework on their own. However, it can be noticed that there were learners who have expressed that they were not into blended learning. This might an impact of the two years gap that they have become more comfortable in attending the other modality of learning.

2.3 Students' Satisfaction in terms of Instructor

The Students' Satisfaction Level in Cabuyao City Private Schools in terms of **Instructor** had a general assessment of **3.35** which was verbally interpreted as **Strongly Agree or Very Satisfied**.

All indicators were verbally interpreted as Very Satisfied. Furthermore, the indicator *"The instructor makes me feel that I am a true member of the class"* had the highest computed mean of 3.43 meanwhile, the indicator *"The instructor uses blended learning technology appropriately"* had the lowest computed mean of 3.30.

Table 2.3

Students' Satisfaction Level in Cabuyao City Private Schools in terms of Instructor

Indicators in terms of Instructor	$\bar{X}$	VI	Rank
1. The instructor makes me feel that I am a true member of the class.	3.43	SA	1
2. I am satisfied with the accessibility and availability of the instructor.	3.33	SA	4

3. The instructor uses blended learning technology appropriately.	3.30	SA	5
4. Class assignments were clearly communicated to me.	3.35	SA	2
5. Feedback on evaluation of tests and other assignments was given in a timely manner.	3.34	SA	3
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.35	SA/VS	

Legend:

3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/ Very Satisfied

2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A)/ Satisfied

1.75 – 2.49 Disagree (D)/ Dissatisfied

1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/ Very Dissatisfied

The result implies that the learners have expressed their Strong Agreement that their instructor have made them feel that they are part of the class. This tantamount to say that the learners themselves have felt the concern of their teachers who were able to show the learners that they care for them, and they are significant members of the class. On the other hand, it was also disclosed in the assessment of the learners that there is still a need for the instructors to improve their capabilities to execute the blended learning technology appropriately. This means also that the teachers shall be equipped enough with the various technology that might be used in teaching their learners in the blended learning modality.

2.4 Students' Satisfaction in terms of Course Management

Table 2.4

Students' Satisfaction Level in Cabuyao City Private Schools in terms of Course Management

Indicators in terms of Course Management	$\bar{X}$	VI	Rank
1. Discipline is highly observed when the lecturer is on the other side of the blended learning classroom.	3.42	SA	2
2. The lecturer/supervisor always takes attendance.	3.45	SA	1
3. I attend videoconferencing classes the same way I attend face-to-face classes.	3.40	SA	3
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.42	SA/VS	

Legend:

3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/ Very Satisfied

2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A)/ Satisfied

1.75 – 2.49 Disagree (D)/ Dissatisfied

1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/ Very Dissatisfied

The students' satisfaction level in Cabuyao City Private Schools in terms of **Course Management** had a general assessment of **3.42** which was verbally interpreted as **Strongly Agree or Very Satisfied**.

All indicators were verbally interpreted as Very Satisfied. Furthermore, the indicator *"The lecturer/supervisor always takes attendance"* had the highest computed mean of 3.45 meanwhile, the indicator *"I attend videoconferencing classes the same way I attend face-to-face classes"* had the lowest computed mean of 3.40.

As disclosed by the results, the students have Very Satisfied that their teachers take attendance. They are very satisfied that their teachers have checked if they are attending the classes during the blended learning. This means that the teachers check the attendance both in online and in physical classes. It is a way of ensuring that the learners are attending the classes, and a way of showing how interested the learners are in attending their classes.

2.5 Students' Satisfaction in terms of Technology

The students' satisfaction level in Cabuyao City Private Schools in terms of **Technology** had a general assessment of **3.23** which was verbally interpreted as **Agree or Satisfied**.

Table 2.5

Students' Satisfaction Level in Cabuyao City Private Schools in terms of Technology

Indicators in terms of Technology	$\bar{X}$	VI	Rank
1. The instructor's voice is audible.	3.29	SA	1.5
2. Course content shown or displayed on the smart board is clear.	3.29	SA	1.5
3. The microphone is in good working condition.	3.24	A	5
4. The video image is clear and comprehensive when the lecturer is on the other side of the blended learning classroom.	3.27	SA	3.5
5. Technical problems are not frequent and they do not adversely affect my understanding of the course.	3.03	A	6
6. The technology used for blended teaching is reliable.	3.27	SA	3.5
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.23	A/S	

Legend:

3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/ Very Satisfied

2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A)/ Satisfied

1.75 – 2.49 Disagree (D)/ Dissatisfied

1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/ Very Dissatisfied

Most of the indicators were verbally interpreted as Very Satisfied. Furthermore, the indicators “*The instructor’s voice is audible*” and “*Course content shown or displayed on the smart board is clear*” had the highest computed mean of 3.29 meanwhile, the indicator “*Technical problems are not frequent and they do not adversely affect my understanding of the course*” had the lowest computed mean of 3.03.

As divulged in the table, the learners have Strongly Agreed that the teacher’s voice is audible and also, course content shown or displayed on the smart board is clear. This means that during the blended learning, the technology using by the teachers bring audible voice of the teachers which clearly heard by the learners. And also, the smart board is clear. These are the major components of teaching that should be offered by the technology during the online class. The teachers who give the instructions shall be heard by the learners, and the smart board where the teachers present the lesson and their explanation shall be clear enough for the learners.

As shown in the results, the students have assessed that they sometimes encountered technological error that affect their studies. This further means that during the blended learning, teachers have less control on their means of delivery of instruction which is through an online platform. Hence, they cannot something when an error in the technological aspect occurred.

Johannes (2021) explained that one of the major problems encountered during the online distance learning is the technological errors. The wifi signal, the power outage, and other related technological problem may affect the ability of the teachers to connect with the learners and to deliver the instruction with them.

Research Question 3. Is there a significant difference between the assessed level of blended learning implementation of teachers and students in Cabuyao City Private Schools?

Table 3

Test of Significant Difference on the Assessment of the Teachers and Students in Cabuyao City Private Schools on the Level of Blended Learning Implementation

Sub-variables		Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F Ratio	Sig .	Remarks	Decision
Pedagogical Design	Between Groups	.761	1	.761	2.953	.087	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
	Within	58.996	229	.258				

	Groups	59.75	23					
	Total	7	0					
	Between	1.724	1					
	Groups	50.48	22	1.72				
Social Design	Within	8	9	4	7.822	.006	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Groups	52.21	23	.220				
	Total	2	0					
	Between	3.127	1					
	Groups	66.61	22	3.12				
Technical Design	Within	0	9	7	10.752	.001	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Groups	69.73	23	.291				
	Total	7	0					

Level of significance 0.05

Table 3 discloses the significant difference on the assessments of the teachers and students in Cabuyao City Private Schools on the level of Blended Learning Implementation. As disclosed by the table, among the principles under the blended learning such as Social Design (0.006) and Technical Design (0.001) with their affixed p-value which are both less than 0.05 were found to have significant difference. This leads to reject the null hypothesis. And therefore, the teachers and the students have significant difference in the assessments of the level of blended learning Implementation in terms of Social Design and Technical Design.

On the other hand, among the principles of the implementation of the Blended Learning, the Pedagogical Design (0.087) with its attached p-values greater than 0.05 was found to accept the null hypothesis. Therefore the teachers and the learners have no significant difference on their assessments toward the level of implementation of blended learning in terms of Pedagogical Design.

The result implies that the teachers and the learners have perceived the implementation of the Blended Learning in terms of Social Design and Technical Design differently. Which means that the teachers or the learners might have lower or higher assessment towards this principles of blended learning. Further, there are aspects of the blended learning which the learners may have less knowledge as compare to teachers. The learners might have limited knowledge concerning these areas and cannot fully understand its worth to the implementation of the Blended learning.

This means that the teachers and the students have similar perceptions towards Pedagogical Design. Teachers' view about how the pedagogical design in the implementation of the blended learning is what being felt and observed by the students.

A teacher's primary responsibility is to ensure that the students grasp the performance requirements and the content standards. Therefore, a solid foundation of knowledge within and across the curriculum teaching areas is the key tool in teaching, which teachers will utilize to construct teaching instructions for learners' target skills.

Research Question 4. Is there a significant relationship between the assessed level of blended learning implementation and students' satisfaction in Cabuyao City Private Schools?

For the test of significant relationship between the level of blended learning implementation and students' satisfaction in Cabuyao City Private Schools, the r values ranging from .599 to .738 were interpreted as with moderate positive to high positive correlation as to correlate Blended Learning Implementation in terms of Pedagogical Design, Social Design, and Technical Design and Students' Satisfaction in terms of Interaction, Instruction, Instructor, Course Management, and Technology. The computed probability values .000 were lesser than the level of significant ($P < 0.05$); thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. The result shows that there is a significant relationship between the independent and dependent variables.

Table 4

Test of Significant Relationship between the Level of Blended Learning Implementation and Students' Satisfaction in Cabuyao City Private Schools

Level of Blended Learning Implementation	Students' Satisfaction	r value	P value	Remarks	Decision
Pedagogical Design	Interaction	.726**	.000	Significant	Reject H_0
	Instruction	.726**	.000	Significant	Reject H_0
	Instructor	.701**	.000	Significant	Reject H_0
	Course Management	.639**	.000	Significant	Reject H_0
	Technology	.733**	.000	Significant	Reject H_0
Social Design	Interaction	.649**	.000	Significant	Reject H_0
	Instruction	.635**	.000	Significant	Reject H_0
	Instructor	.674**	.000	Significant	Reject H_0
	Course Management	.619**	.000	Significant	Reject H_0
Technical Design	Technology	.660**	.000	Significant	Reject H_0
	Interaction	.738**	.000	Significant	Reject H_0

Instruction	.734**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
Instructor	.673**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
Course Management	.599**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
Technology	.661**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀

**Correlational at the level 0.01
0.05(Two-tailed)

*Correlational at the level

It can be concluded that blended learning implementation has a high significant relationship with the students' satisfaction in Cabuyao City Private Schools. This further implies that the better the implementation of the Blended Learning, the higher the student's satisfactions will be. This further implies that the learners have been satisfied to the implementation of the blended learning of their school. Likewise, the activities and services offered by the school during the blended learning have satisfied and meet the expectations of the learners.

With the use of learning management systems like Blackboard, Moodle, and WebCT, teachers might connect with their students while also assessing them and keeping tabs on their progress through a variety of learning aids in electronic learning. Education had been significantly threatened by the global COVID-19 epidemic, which poses a serious threat to human life and activity. Students struggled to follow the course online, which caused them to study for a longer period of time each day. This made it difficult for them to keep up with the course and had an adverse effect on their academic success. Regardless of the fact that many academics had evaluated the degree of student satisfaction in an online learning environment, it was crucial to recognize the impact of e-learning quality on understanding how satisfied students were with the current content and e-learning quality offered in an online learning environment. This was because students had relied heavily on e-learning during the COVID-19 crisis (Mohammed, 2022).

Research Question 5. Based on the findings of the study, what action plan may be proposed?

The implementation of blended learning has been perceived as challenging not just on the side of the learners but even among teachers and the school which shall work hand-in hand to offer the best services for the learners, and to ensure the continuity of learning despite of the pandemic and the challenges it posted.

The private schools have to look into the best ways to offer nothing but the best among its learners. They have to spend time, effort and money to ensure that the learners are provided of the things they deserve. The schools have to make sure that the Pedagogical Design, Social Design and the Technical Design are well-equipped, well

shown, and well implemented. These are the areas that the schools shall provide activities suited to the needs and interest of learners and make them satisfied in all these principles.

From the findings of this study, the researcher was able to propose the Action Plan, which focused on the indicator per principles that attained the lowest results. This is the very core of this study, to discover the problem to propose activities based from the results that would be the ways to address the said problems.

Table 5

The Proposed Action Plan

AREA OF CONCERN	OBJECTIVES	STRATEGIES/ ACTIVITIES	TIME FRAME	PERSONS INVOLVED	SOURCE OF FUND	SUCCESS INDICATORS
The structure of the environment that helps focus on learning	To ensure that the environment helps the students focus on learning.	Survey Parent's orientation	August 2023 – September 2023	Students and Parents Teachers School Admin	Personal Budget	90% of the students have been ensured to have an environment that helps to focus on learning.
Regular evaluation of student-to-students' activities	To practice regular peer evaluation	Group Activities Think-Pair-Share Numbered Heads Together	August 2023 – May 2024	Students Teachers	Classroom Budget	90% of the class will be able to share their work to their classmates and evaluate it.
Students' preferred time to learn/study	To encourage the students about the best time to study	Mental Health Seminar Peer discussion	March 2023 (Mental Health Month)	Students Teachers HR Guidance Office	School Fund	90% of the students and teachers attested that mental health is important as well as the management of school responsibilities.
Gender sensitivity that restricts from learning	To ensure that the students recognizes the gender equality	Gender Equality Seminar Coaching/ Mentoring	March 2023 (Gender Equality Month)	Students and Parents Teachers School Staff	School Fund	95% of the students and teachers appreciates and respects the gender equality.

Blended learning experiences compared to traditional course setting	To guarantee that blended learning is satisfying like any other learning modality	Curriculum Planning Teachers and Head Coaching/ Mentoring	July 2023 – September 2023	Teachers Subject Coordinators Head Teachers School Admin Teachers	School Fund	95% success a satisfying blended learning experiences.
Appropriate use of technology in blended learning	To train teachers on proper way of using technology in blended learning set up	Teachers' Induction Program	July 2023 – August 2023	Subject Coordinators Head Teachers	School Fund	95% of the participants have been trained to use technology in blended learning.
Participation in video conferencing and in face to face classes	To make sure that students are attending classes same in video conferencing and in face-to-face classes.	Regular checking of students' attendance Same weight of activities/ discussion in online and face-to-face classes Regular Checking of the Platform used	August 2023 – October 2023	Teachers and Students	School Fund	95% of the students are attending classes both in video conferencing and in face-to-face classes.
Technical problems encountered in blended learning.	To ensure that technical problems are not frequent in blended learning	Providing and checking good internet connection Giving safe and conducive face-to-face classroom for learning	July 2023 – December 2023	Teachers Head Teachers School Admin IT Department School Structural Engineers	School Fund	90% of the students are satisfy in blended learning and will not or at least minimal encounter in terms of technical problems.

DISCUSSION

The following are the salient findings of the study:

1. Level of Blended Learning in Cabuyao City Private Schools

In terms of Pedagogical Design, Social Design, and Technical Design, the general assessments are 3.45, 3.44, and 3.39 respectively and were verbally interpreted as Strongly Agree of Fully Implemented.

2. Students' Satisfaction Level in Cabuyao City Private Schools

In terms of Interaction, Instruction, Instructor, Course Management, and Technology it attained a general assessment of 3.17, 3.21, 3.35, 3.42, and 3.23 respectively which were verbally interpreted as Satisfied to Very Satisfied.

3. Test of Significant Difference on the Assessment of the Teachers and Students on the Level of Blended Learning Implementation

Among the principles under the blended learning such as Social Design (0.006) and Technical Design (0.001) with their affixed p-value which are both less than 0.05 were found to have significant different. This leads to reject the null hypothesis. The teachers and the students have different assessments on the level of blended learning implementation in terms of Social Design and Technical Design.

On the other hand, the Pedagogical Design (0.087) with its attached p-values greater than 0.05 was found to accept the null hypothesis. Therefore, the teachers and the learners have no significant difference on their assessments toward the level of implementation of blended learning in terms of Pedagogical Design.

4. Test of Significant Relationship between the Level of Blended Learning Implementation and Students' Satisfaction in Cabuyao City Private Schools

On the test of significant relationship between the level of blended learning implementation and students' satisfaction in Cabuyao City Private Schools, the r values ranging from .599 to .738 were interpreted as with moderate positive to high positive correlation as to correlate Blended Learning Implementation in terms of Pedagogical Design, Social Design, and Technical Design and Students' Satisfaction in terms of Interaction, Instruction, Instructor, Course Management, and Technology. The computed probability values .000 were lesser than the level of significant ($P < 0.05$); thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. The result shows that there is a significant relationship between the independent and dependent variables.

5. The Proposed Action Plan

As an output, an Action Plan is proposed which is intended for the use of the private schools to maintain their good practices in the implementation of the Blended Learning. This also includes the activities that have to be implemented to be able to improve the indicators that attained the lowest assessments from the respondents of this study. Through this output, the learners will be more satisfied to the services catered by the private schools to its learners.

Conclusions

1. That the teachers were able to craft and state the objectives clearly and can be attained at the end of the lesson. However, there is still a need to re-structure or improve

the structure of learning environment which might help the learners attain better focus on their studies. The learners might have better condition and interest for learning if they have harmonious social relationship with usual people they are dealing with such as the teachers and their classmates. On the other hand, it turned out that learners have given less agreement on evaluating the works of their classmates. This might be due to the fact that their teachers conduct less activities that would enable the learner to check the work of their classmates. Students can study in their most convenient time. With the combination of face to face classes and online classes, students has the additional time to study even after the school hours since they are in their comfort place and time – their home. Blended learning which provides time for the learners to accomplish the tasks on their convenient time, when they are in the mood, when they are at the height of their interests to do their learning tasks.

2. That the students still able to interact with their peers and their teachers even on the other side of the virtual classroom. The result also indicate that the learners love to see and deal with their teachers and classmates physically. On the other hand, the learners still have an issue towards the opposite gender, they feel being restricted. This shows that the learners still have to understand the GAD or gender and equality in learning. The learners have expressed that they were Satisfied when regards to the level of effort required by the course they are taking. Also, they were able to apply what they have learned. These are the very core of authentic learning, that the learners understand the course they are taking and how they apply it to their daily lives. However, that there were learners who have expressed that they were not into blended learning. This might an impact of the two years gap that they have become more comfortable in attending the other modality of learning. The students have expressed their Strong Agreement that their instructor have made them feel that they are part of the class. They themselves have felt the concern of their teachers who were able to show the learners that they care for them, and they are significant members of the class. On the other hand, there is still a need for the instructors to improve their capabilities to execute the blended learning technology appropriately. This means also that the teachers shall be equipped enough with the various technology that might be used in teaching their learners in the blended learning modality. The students are Very Satisfied that their teachers take attendance. They are very satisfied that their teachers have checked if they are attending the classes during the blended learning. This means that the teachers check the attendance both in online and in physical classes. It is a way of ensuring that the learners are attending the classes, and a way of showing how interested the learners are in attending their classes. The teacher's voice is audible and also, course content shown or displayed on the smart board is clear. The technology used by the teachers bring audible voice of the teachers which clearly heard by the students. And also, the smart board is clear. These are the major components of teaching that should be offered by the technology during the online class. On the other hand, the students sometimes encountered technological error that affect their studies. This further means that during the blended learning, teachers have less control on their means of delivery of instruction which is through an online platform.

3. That the teachers and the students have perceived the implementation of the Blended Learning in terms of Social Design and Technical Design differently. Which

means that the teachers or the learners might have lower or higher assessment towards this principles of blended learning. Further, there are aspects of the blended learning which the learners may have less knowledge as compare to teachers. The learners might have limited knowledge concerning these areas and cannot fully understand its worth to the implementation of the Blended learning. The teachers and the students have similar perceptions towards Pedagogical Design. Teachers' view about how the pedagogical design in the implementation of the blended learning is what being felt and observed by the students.

4. That the learners have been satisfied with the implementation of the blended learning of their school. Likewise, the activities and services offered by the school during the blended learning have satisfied and meet the expectations of the learners.

5. That the proposed action plan is a big help in assisting the schools on its implementation of the Blended Learning in the three major principles such as Pedagogical, Social, and Technical Designs to be able to sustain the satisfactions of students.

Recommendations

1. The private schools are encouraged to expose the teachers to the various Professional Training focused on maintaining well-conducive learning environment. The teachers are also advised to conduct activities that would enable the learners to validate their performance of others while maintaining positive atmosphere as a way of improving the social aspect of learners. The private schools are heartened to conduct continuous monitoring and evaluation of the conduct of the various activities in the Blended Learning that will be benefited by both teachers and their students.
2. The private schools might take responsibilities to conduct GAD training for the learners and their teachers. The private schools are advised to strengthen the advocacy campaign about the relevance of the blended learning. The teachers in the private schools are also encouraged to attend professional development activities and program that would help them improve their knowledge on the utilization of ICT on their respective classes. Attendance checking is encouraged to be facilitated religiously both in face-to-face and online learning or classes. Internet connectivity of the schools shall have been enhanced to avoid connectivity issue that would hamper the conduct of the online learning.
3. Both teachers and the students shall have been provided series of training and workshops related to Social Design and Technical Design that would be a way of making them more aware of its nature and importance to attain better implementation of Blended Learning.
4. The private schools are encouraged to implement monthly Monitoring and Evaluation of the implementation of the Blended learning in three of its major

principles such as the Pedagogical, Social and Technical Design to ensure that the learners will be satisfied with the services of the private schools and their interest will also be maintained.

5. The proposed action plan might be adapted by the private schools that would enable them to enhance the implementation of the Blended Learning satisfying the needs of learners and attain the goal of being part of DepEd in producing quality graduates despite of the challenges posted by the pandemic.
 6. Future researchers may consider pursuing this study by connecting the next possibilities that might happen in the educational set up, given that there will be many possible setbacks that might be present in the future that will affect the learning delivery.
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Compliance with Ethical Standards

The consideration of these issues were necessary to ensure privacy and security of participants. Among the significant ethical issues considered in the research process include consent and confidentiality. The researchers relayed all the important details and the aim of the study to secure consent from the respondents. By explaining these vital details, respondents were to understand their role in the completion of the study. The confidentiality of the respondents was ensured by not disclosing their names where they are currently affiliated. Only relevant information needed to answer the specific research questions will be included. The data pooled in this study were kept confidential and were solely used for the purpose of this study. Also, this study undergo a plagiarism test, and its Turnitin Similarity Index was 15%.

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